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Use of Technology for Peer Learning in the Study of the Russian Language by Chinese Interns

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Abstract

The article examines the formation of speech interaction skills and the development of teamwork in the process of mastering the stylistic features of the Russian language by Chinese trainees. The use of innovative learning technologies contributes to the achievement of these goals, including interactive technology of mutual learning as one of the most important components of educational communication.

The author points at the most important competencies that trainees need for successful learning and mastering the skills of speech interaction in Russian. These include, first of all, communicative competence, which includes language, discursive, conversational, pragmatic (practical), socio-linguistic, strategic and thinking competence. The formation of interpersonal relationships is considered in connection with the formation of a differentiated impact on the communication partner.

The main attention is paid to the ways and methods of interactive learning, in which three-level interaction between the teacher and students is carried out, at the levels of educational content, interpersonal relations and self-awareness. The article summarizes the experience of working with Chinese trainees in the process of teaching them to read texts of different styles in Russian classes.

Keywords: mutual learning technologies, educational communication, communicative competence, student activation, Russian; non-native language.

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Introduction

The increasing role of communication in modern society, the need to develop skills of cooperation, interaction in heterogeneous groups and the development of teamwork to solve complex problems cause the actualization of pedagogical knowledge in the field of communication organization based on traditional and innovative learning technologies.

It is known that in the methodological literature, the word communication (from lat. *communico* – general) means the joint activity of participants in speech communication. Speech communication is one of the activities in which the subject's consciousness focuses on the thoughts that he seeks to communicate to his partner (speaking, writing), and on the information that is transmitted to him in verbal form (reading, listening). At the same time, communication, being a psychological action, rarely acts as an independent activity, more often being part of a more complex activity, a means of achieving some non-verbal goal (Leontiev, 1974). Usually, this is a directed interaction of people with each other, mediated by language and speech. The purpose of this interaction is the process of exchanging between people certain results of their activities: learned information, thoughts and judgments, assessments, feelings, experiences and attitudes. It is speech activity that is the object of language learning, through mastering the means, methods, mechanisms of which the learner himself is formed.

Depending on the subject of activity, methodists Mitrofanova and Kostomarov (1990) distinguish various types of it. These are:

- cognitive activity ensuring the formation, storage and operation of required samples, models of the real world (for without the knowledge of the reality of no activity possible);
- value-orientation which establishes the relationship between the object or subject of activity, resulting in a value orientation with regard to the spiritual needs and aspirations of the individual;
- operationally instrumental (or conversion technology), which can be directed at the real object, i.e. to be practical;
- communication related to the communication, the interaction of subjects, understood as communication at this time, as well as past and future, communication is both direct and mediated by cultural objects.

The formation and development of the above-mentioned activities is the prerogative of the language teaching methodology.

Note that the concept of communication in scientific literature is also used to characterize the specifics of interaction and communication between representatives of various ethnic communities. According to Krysko (2001), the culture of interethnic communication in the content plan includes a set of special knowledge and skills, as well as appropriate actions and actions that are manifested in interpersonal contacts and interaction of representatives of various ethnic communities and allow quickly and painlessly achieve mutual understanding and agreement in the common interests. The culture of interethnic communication is an organic component of the spiritual life of society, its culture, in particular, the culture of human relations in general.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the research is to reveal the specifics of using interactive structures of mutual learning technology as one of the most important components of educational communication when learning Russian by Chinese trainees.

Literature review

The problem of teaching communication in a second language has received a fairly deep theoretical justification in the works of famous scientists-psychologists and methodologists Vygotsky (1982), Yacobson (1985), Gromkova (2003), Levin (2001), Piaget (2003), Leontiev (1974), Yakimanskaya (2000), Ter-Minasova (2000), Kagan (1990), Zimnaya (1992), Passov (1991), Vezhbitskaya (1999), Matyash (2004) and others.

Based on the results of fundamental research of these scientists, it can be established that communication is an important condition for the mental development of a person, his sociologization and individualization, and the formation of personality. Communication is a subjective-subjective relationship of people, each of whom is characterized by activity, consciously directed planning and organization of their behavior. Communication partners influence each other in a certain way, perceive and evaluate each other. Thus, referring to the opinion of Gromkova (2003), it can be argued that interaction always involves communication, i.e. the exchange of information for the purpose of understanding. Understanding is a necessary condition for communication, its purpose and result, without which it (communication) does not make sense.

That is why it becomes an objective necessity to develop a methodological system that would ensure the acquisition of language in its main functions – as a means of communication, communication and cognition, planning and organizing activities (especially collective), emotional, aesthetic and moral impact and education – with the priority of the communicative function.

New approaches to teaching Russian (as well as other languages) are viewed in the context of an organic relationship with the student's personality, taking into account their interests, needs and value orientations.

The leading value in the cognitive activity of students is acquired by the complex mastering of skills of cooperation and productive communication in the language being studied. These activities are formed and developed in the process of applying mutual learning-technology of interactive group interaction of all participants.

Despite the fact that modern pedagogical science is rich an Arsenal of interactive approaches (to date, developed more than 200 structures – sequential steps, educational strategies aimed at structuring the interactions of learners with each other, with the teacher and/or content), however, methodologists in the field of language learning continue to seek best practices in the educational process of educational technologies of communication, conducive to the mastery of linguistic tools, speech and ethical competence and reading skills in the target language as a means of learning and self-education.

A number of serious studies are still to be done to study the interaction of participants in different fields of knowledge and different language backgrounds, because, first, currently the possibilities of comparing languages in terms of speech activity are limited since we do not yet have sufficient knowledge about all the methodically relevant operations that underlie speech actions, and, secondly, the issues of forming Russian speech skills are often considered without taking into account the laws of the communication process and its mechanisms. The main thing in communication is the conjugacy and mutual reversibility of the actions of its participants. For the development of communication skills, i.e. the ability to communicate in a second language, it is necessary to activate the student. His success is the result of his personal activity.

The formation of Chinese trainees 'communicative competence, including language, discursive, conversational, pragmatic (practical), socio-linguistic, strategic and thinking competence, occurs in the process of mastering the main factors, principles and rules of speech communication in Russian, methods of speech influence, role structure of speech behavior, strategy and tactics of conversation, the many hidden meanings that are transmitted in the process of exchanging replicas.

Methodology

When choosing research methods, we relied on the provision that in the course of interactive learning, which is a dialogue training, in which students actively interact with both the teacher and each other, there is a three-level interaction between the teacher and students:

- 1) the level of educational content (access to the understanding of educational material and educational information);
- 2) the level of interpersonal relations (access to communication strategies and tactics);
- 3) the level of self-awareness (access to self-control, reflection of communicative abilities and communicative actions).

Experience with trainees has confirmed that this three-level dialogue training-interaction contributes to the assimilation of the content of the discipline "Reading texts of different styles" and the acquisition of social competencies by means of communication strategies and tactics.

During the course of the academic discipline "Reading texts of different styles", trainees must master the following competencies that they will need to successfully master the other disciplines: independent work with information; presentation skills; communication skills (readiness to communicate in oral and written forms to solve professional tasks); skills of working in collaboration; skills of analyzing problem situations, finding ways to solve the educational problem; practical skills in project activities of searching, collecting and processing information (skills of reading, understanding and highlighting the main idea of the read source text); possession of several speech styles.

An important condition for inclusion in educational cooperation through communication is informative competence. The silent student in class often due to the fact that he does not own the subject has no personal relationship to the problem under discussion, not familiar with the possible ways of behavior. The formation of informative competence of trainees is formed in the process of mastering a meaningful subject of communication with information frames (or scenarios of situations); a language picture of the world in its foreign language form, background knowledge in professional training, as well as a General Outlook.

Research in the field of frame semantics clearly shows that the frame is of great importance for the perception and generation of a speech utterance. Thus, Deik van (1988) rightly States that the speaker can only successfully carry out the intended speech act when he is sure that the pragmatic context satisfies the conditions of this speech act.

Experiment description and procedure

The reliance on the scientific and methodological provisions of communication-oriented teaching has led to the fact that when studying Russian, trainees better master certain skills if they are allowed to approach the subject through their own experience; they learn better if the teacher actively supports their way of learning; they perceive the material better if the teacher, on the one hand, structures the subject for easier learning, on the other hand, accepts and includes in the discussion their opinions of students who do not coincide with their own point of view.

It should be noted that the implementation of the goals of interpersonal relations is carried out in a communicative strategy using speech tactics. The strategy of speech communication covers the entire sphere of building the communication process when the goal is to achieve some long-term results. Usually, there are 10 such strategies (styles) (Krysko, 2001): dominant, dramatic, controversial, calming, impressive, accurate, attentive, inspired, friendly, and open.

The tactic of speech communication describes a set of techniques for conducting a conversation and a line of behavior at a certain stage in a separate conversation aimed at achieving the desired effect or preventing an undesirable result. The tactic of speech communication also describes specific speech actions aimed at achieving impact at a certain stage of communication, attracting attention, establishing and maintaining contact, persuading or persuading the recipient, bringing him to a certain emotional state, etc. Tactics of verbal communication may have more than strategy to change depending on changing conditions of communication, the views expressed by the interviewee, feelings and emotions, discover the information about yourself, announce in the course of the conversation the Focus of various tactics to achieve a certain communicative purpose built in some strategy, and in this sense, the strategy and tactics are interdependent and the boundaries between these phenomena are not always clear.

Possession of the strategy and tactics of speech communication is more based on the speaker's possession of variable speech means. Every minute the speaker chooses the most appropriate lexical and grammatical variants of transmitting thoughts and feelings, the most appropriate options for developing the conversation, the most effective solutions to emerging communication problems and problems, the most appropriate options for responding to the interlocutor's remarks.

Modern pedagogy is rich in a whole Arsenal of interactive approaches, including creative tasks, work in small groups, educational games (role-playing, business and educational games); the use of public resources (invitation of a specialist, excursions); social projects and other extracurricular methods of teaching (competitions, interviews, films, performances, exhibitions); the study and consolidation of new

material (interactive lectures, work with visual AIDS, video and audio materials, "learning as a teacher", "mosaic" ("Everyone teaches everyone"), the use of "thick" and "subtle" questions, Socratic dialogue); feedback; distance learning; discussion of complex and debatable issues and problems (take a stand, scale of opinions, pop formula); problem resolution ("decision tree", "brainstorming", "case analysis"); training.

Results

Group activities can be used at any time in the class: at the beginning of the class - to focus the trainees' attention on the material being studied, during the text and post - text work - to facilitate the trainees' understanding of the content, or at the end of the class - to summarize the results.

In order to maintain the active intellectual involvement of trainees throughout the class, we periodically used various strategies, among which the most effective was the technology of group mutual learning "mosaic" ("Everyone teaches everyone": Read - Think - Work in a group - Share what you read). In the process of applying this technology, students form groups to work on the academic material being studied, which is divided into parts. Each member of the group reads their own part, becoming an expert in its content and preparing to teach this information to other members of the group. Then members of different groups who have studied information from the same part meet in "expert groups" to discuss it. Students then return to their original groups and take turns teaching their part of the information to other group members. Participants rely on each other to reproduce their own part of the material and transmit it effectively. When all members of the group have taught their parts and learned parts of the material of their fellows, the teacher is able to conduct testing, ask students to write group reports on the content, or conduct an oral survey using the technology of "thick and thin questions" (akin to the game "Own game").

When constructing knowledge using mutual learning, reflection is important as it helps students to fix their level of development and self-development, as well as the reasons for achieving or not achieving successful results. In this regard, trainees are always eager to share their impressions using marker words (I Know! I can! Hurray! I manage! Great! Difficult! Help!), and also give an assessment of their work and the work of their classmates, continuing the sentences: I liked the explanation (about what?), because I would like to learn more (about what?) ... I liked the explanation (whose?) becauseIt was hard for me to understand I still don't understand

An equally important means of interactive interaction between trainees is the technology of educational communication which facilitates group research in extracurricular time. When using this method of mutual learning, they participate in planning the stages of the research process. At the first stage, trainees form a group on the research topic that interests them, while the genre diversity of texts in the study of the

discipline contributes to the development of skills for producing, analyzing and evaluating different types of fiction and scientific products. In the second stage, they plan to work together to complete the study, distributing the actions of each group member and drawing up an action plan. In the third stage, trainees conduct research, during which they collect material, then select the necessary information and structure it, then prepare a plan and/or theses, exchange the collected and structured information with the trainees of their group, analyze the data, understand, synthesize thoughts throughout the research process and then come to a certain conclusion. The final design of the written research text is prepared by trainees at the fourth stage, and at the fifth stage, it is presented. Finally, at the sixth stage, trainees evaluate their work (reflection).

Discussions

The effectiveness of mutual learning can only be high when the trainees are psychologically prepared to work together in the interests of joint learning, manifested in positive interdependence when the goal is achieved only by helping each other, individual responsibility for their contribution, equal participation and simultaneous interaction of all trainees.

Trainees come to understand that when learning a second language, you need to not just learn words by topic, but learn to use various speech techniques. Of great interest in the analysis of the communication process is the concept of Bern (2014), which interprets from a psychological point of view the concept of a role as a repertoire of speech actions that a person must perform under certain circumstances. The concept of a role is related to the concept of a game used by Bern (2014). The game is a form of interaction between people when communicating and can be quite serious. The game includes a series of communication units. By talking to another person, or simply by showing that they are aware of each other's presence, people provide a stimulus that is followed by some response. The purpose of the analysis, according to the method of Bern (2014), is to understand what the human condition is responsible for the stimulus and a reaction. In normal human relationships, a stimulus entails an appropriate, expected, and natural response.

Conclusion

Thus, the basis of interactive training of Chinese trainees to communicate in Russian is the formation of a communicative competence that integrates a set of factors. These include the definition and justification of areas, topics and situations of communication, the possession of various tactics of speech behavior depending on the speech intentions of communicants, the selection and assimilation of language tools necessary for communication ("playing" roles) with an emphasis on stylistic variation.

During interactive learning to read and understand the main and non-main (additional) content of texts of different styles, we identified the most significant speech needs of differentiated impact on the communication partner (highlighted by us-DM). Their Active implementation in both dialogic and monologue speech leads to the fact that the Russian language learners' own statements become manageable and controlled. They develop an individual style of speech, its structure becomes more complex, and special terms, abstract and metaphorical expressions appear.

The natural result of the research was a deepening of motivation for learning the Russian language, as well as a higher culture of speech of trainees, which consists not only in following the norms of the language but also in developing creative independence, giving their activities a research character, stimulating interest in an independent acquisition of new knowledge, contributing to the development of trainees' respect for other peoples, their history and culture.

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